

**JISMONIY TARBIYA DARSLARIDA TA'LIM SAMARADORLIGINI
OSHIRISHNING PEDAGOGIK IMKONIYATLARI**

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**ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ
ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОЙ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ НА УРОКАХ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ
ВОСПИТАНИЯ**

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**PEDAGOGICAL OPPORTUNITIES FOR INCREASING
EDUCATIONAL EFFICIENCY IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION LESSONS**

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada maktablarda jismoniy tarbiya darslarini tashkil qilishda yangi zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanish va ularning dars samaradorligini oshirishdagi ahamiyati to'g'risida ma'lumotlar bayon qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: jismoniy tarbiya, dars, pedagogik texnologiyalar, ta'lim, metodlar, loyihalashtirish, kompyuter texnologiyalari.

Аннотация: В данной статье изложена информация об использовании новых современных педагогических технологий в организации уроков физической культуры в школах и их значении для повышения эффективности уроков.

Ключевые слова: физкультура, урок, педагогические технологии, воспитание, методы, проектирование, компьютерные технологии.

Annotation: This article describes information on the use of new modern pedagogical technologies in the organization of physical education classes in schools and their importance in increasing the effectiveness of the lesson.

Keywords: physical education, lesson, pedagogical technologies, education, methods, design, computer technologies.

Relevance of the topic. Ensuring the prospects of the independent Republic of Uzbekistan at the level of world development is connected with major changes in the economic, social, political and cultural spheres. Participation in such changes requires people to have a high level of general and special knowledge, high culture, spirituality and a broad outlook. Reconstruction of the educational system based on these requirements will serve to meet the needs of the society in the field of education of the future generation.

The technological approach to education is one of the factors that actively influence the pedagogical process and determine its efficiency, integrity and success. The humanization, democratization of the educational system of Uzbekistan and the introduction of new technologies have set difficult tasks for the sciences, such as determining the content, structure, level of development, opportunities and technology of education.

In the current era, it is the demand of the time for teachers to have high professional training, pedagogical skills, high spiritual and moral qualities, deep

knowledge of ideology, effective use of modern pedagogical technologies and interactive methods in educational work.

High scientific, methodical knowledge and practical work of pedagogues as the most important part of the great creative work that is being carried out to ensure that the young generation will grow up to be mature, educated, highly moral, well-rounded and patriotic individuals in all respects. implementation of measures to ensure that they have high skills.

Currently, improving the effectiveness of education in every school is a serious task. For this, every teacher is required to know the most effective modern pedagogical technologies of teaching his subject and to constantly improve his professional skills by continuously studying the innovations in this field. It is known that improving the quality and efficiency of the educational process is the basis of our future development.

The level of study of the research. Abu Ali ibn Sina's service to world science is that he did not only generalize the achievements of scientific thought of the past period to the achievements in the field of medicine, but also developed the science of the Middle Ages. His classic work "Kitab ul Qonun fit tibb" i.e. "The Law of Medical Sciences" spread his fame all over the world. Among the scientists of the world, the services of the famous scientist Abu Ali ibn Sina, who was the first to describe and classify (systematize) physical exercises in his own way, are especially great. Pyotr Franzevich Lesgaft (1837-1909) is an anatomist, biologist, pedagogue, and public figure. YE.N. In Medinsky's words, P.F. Along with the creation of his theory of physical information, Lesgaft completed his work with the theory of family upbringing. The English scientist and philosopher Jean Locke (1632-1704) played a role in the works of the famous French scientist Jean-Jacques Rousseau (1712-1778), the Swedish scientist and pedagogue democrat Johann Heinrich Pestolotsy (1746-1827). J.J. Rousseau and I.G. A new type of school was opened in Germany in the 18th century based on the pedagogical influence of Pestolotsi. These schools are called the school of philanthropists, bourgeois philanthropists. In these schools, more place was given to physical education. Friedrich Ludovic Jahn founded the well-known physical education specialists G. Fit (1763-1836), G.I. Guts-Mutz (1759-1839), a

philanthropist.V.V. Belinovich, K.H. Grantin, N.A. Lupandina, Z.I. Kuznetsova, V.G. Yakovleva, K.D. Novikov, L.P. It was revealed by Matveyev and other scientists. In the following years, the interest in educational technology is clearly visible in the world pedagogical scientific-research works.

Russian pedagogues A.A. Andreyev, V.P. Bepalko, M.T. Gromkova, M.V. Klarin, Mila Noviklar, American pedagogue Bob Kizlik, Uzbek scientists B.R. Adizov, B.L. Farberman, about pedagogical technology, its use in the educational process, ways and methods. It is described in the works of N. Saidahmedov, M. Ochilov, M.H. Mahmudov, S. Ziyamukhamedova, B. Ziyamukhamedov, O. Tolipov.

The purpose of the research: To develop ways and methods of introducing pedagogical technologies in physical education classes.

Research object: The process of introducing pedagogical technologies in physical education classes.

Research subject: Content, form and methods of introducing pedagogical technologies in physical education classes.

Conducting research. Physical education lessons were studied and analyzed in the research. In the 2021-2022 academic year, more than 30-40 physical education lessons were checked and studied in Bogot district schools. The effectiveness of the use of pedagogical technology in the course of physical education was determined. Discussions were held with physical education teachers on new pedagogical technologies for improving lesson efficiency.

The study and analysis of pedagogical literature allows to show the following among the important characteristics and signs of pedagogical technology:

- planning the educational process in advance and re-developing it with students in the classroom;
- drawing up a project of the educational process that describes the student's educational activity based on a systematic approach;
- the goal of education should be realistic, accurate diagnostics and objective assessment of the quality of the student's knowledge acquisition;

- integrity of the structure and content of the educational process, interdependence and mutual influence;
- optimization (facilitation) of forms of education;
- taking into account the interaction of technical means and human potential in the educational process;
- clarification of educational goals as observable and identifiable actions of students on the basis of the target standard;
- teaching based on the student's activity;
- identifying and correcting mistakes made in the process of acquiring knowledge;
- formative and summative assessments;
- performance of test assignments according to established criteria;
- the achievement of the planned result of education is guaranteed;
- high educational efficiency.

As we said above, the requirements for education are huge. It is impossible to fulfill these requirements without applying advanced modern technologies to the educational process. In order to study the level of use of modern technologies in physical education classes, we asked a group of physical education teachers (a total of 20 teachers participated) with the following questions: What do you understand by modern technologies of education?

1. Do you use modern pedagogical technologies of education in your classes?
2. Tell the difference between traditional education and lessons based on pedagogical technologies.
3. How do you understand interactive methods? - Give examples.
4. Do you know modern educational methods and do you implement them in practice?

We evaluated the answers based on the following criteria:

1. It is "very good" if he understands modern technologies well, uses them in his classes, can distinguish them from traditional education and knows interactive methods;

2. It is "good" if he has an understanding of modern technologies, uses them in his experience and knows how they differ from traditional education, and knows some of the interactive methods;

3. Understands modern technologies, but sometimes uses them, if not familiar with interactive methods, "medium".

4. He does not know and did not use modern technologies, sometimes he uses interactive methods "badly".

5. He prefers traditional methods of education and is not interested in modern technologies at all "very bad".

The analysis of the answers is shown in the following table:

The level of use of modern educational technologies by physical education teachers: (in % of respondents)

№	Very good	Good	Medium	Badly	Very bad
1	3	2	8	4	3
2	3	1	4	7	5
3	2	3	6	7	2
4	1	4	5	5	5

The analysis of the table shows that in most of the schools we conducted research, the organization of the educational process based on modern technologies is slow. When it comes to modern technologies, many people complain about the lack of computers at school. They want to justify those who do not use modern technologies in education. However, there are 2 different ways of using pedagogical technologies in education.

The second is to organize classes with the help of computers.

So it is possible to organize classes using modern technologies even without computers. The characteristic aspects of the lesson, its difference from other forms of physical education are as follows. It is clearly expressed, didactically directed, conditioned by the solution of the educational task. The leadership role of the teacher, who is focused on teaching the subject and educating students. Strict study and

determination of student activities and load standards. Continuity of employees and uniformity of their age. The organization of such a teaching process imposes certain requirements on the modern physical education class.

1. The teacher must provide each lesson with a high-level idea. Therefore, it is necessary to plan a modern lesson with complex tasks. Tasks should be defined and differentiated. It is necessary to conduct these activities based on the knowledge of individual mental and physical characteristics of students' development.

2. Each lesson is closely connected with the previous and subsequent lessons and should form a lesson system. When learning a new material, teachers need to review and consolidate the previous material and prepare to master the next material. Such systems ensure the sequence of solving educational tasks.

3. The modern lesson is distinguished by the fact that students' activities are well organized independently. The teacher successively equips them with knowledge and skills in their educational work, develops the need for independent knowledge and self-control, the formation of movement culture, and at the same time, the need for regular physical exercise.

4. All this is done on the basis of color work discipline. The diversity, resources, methods and methods used by the teacher, the organization of the activities of the students, are modern teaching methods. Lessons should never be organized in the same template.

5. It is a condition of efficiency that all students can easily reach movement activities throughout each lesson.

6. It is necessary to ensure that the teacher has a knowledge control system in each lesson, determines the knowledge and skills of students in each part of the lesson, evaluates and develops physical quality at the end of the teaching process.

7. There are many requirements for passing the class: educational material, hygienic, aesthetic, will-psychological, and others. Mentioned students derive from the general and methodical principles of physical education and are mandatory for all classes.

In conclusion, it can be said that the development of our independent country requires major reforms in the field of physical education as well as in all areas of education. Training of competitive personnel is the most necessary condition for meeting the important needs of society. In order to meet the society's need for highly qualified competitive personnel, it is necessary to search and discover new effective methods of education from the primary school. The concept underlying our research is to increase students' motivation to study and to cultivate their interest and need to learn science using pedagogical technology in the process of primary education. The existence of a motive helps to ensure that a person freely engages in educational activities, the formation of free communication between the teacher and the student, and the ability to quickly find a language. During our research, we learned the following:

1. The best experiences of teachers regarding the use of pedagogical technology in physical education classes;

2. We have made sure that there are very few experiences of using pedagogical technology in the educational process. Our research has proven the correctness of our work hypothesis. That is, the introduction of pedagogical technologies in physical education classes, the comprehensive development of study motives, the achievement of an understanding of the essence of pedagogical technology, the in-depth acquisition of relevant knowledge, skills and competencies and their successful use in educational practice during physical education classes. ensures high efficiency. During our research, we used new forms and methods of improving physical education classes. As a result of our research, we came to the following conclusion: One of the most important tasks of education at the present time is the implementation of pedagogical technologies.

1. In the process of physical education classes, if attention is paid to the development of study motives in all aspects, the processes of students' knowledge acquisition will be effective.

2. It is necessary to improve the system of physical education. This system should be aimed at opening the way for students to think freely on the basis of student-teacher cooperation.

3. If the modular study method is used in the course of physical education lessons, a wide path will be opened for students to think freely and independently.

4. We believe that it is possible to achieve the expected results if we use the above-recommended work system in physical education classes.

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